

ISSN 3026 - 8451

GAMJI JOURNAL

OF ARTS AND HUMANITIES

VOL 1 - ISSUE 1

|

JAN - JUN, 2024

A PUBLICATION OF

GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING
AND RESEARCH

GAMJI

JOURNAL OF ARTS AND HUMANITIES

VOL 1, ISSUE 1

JANUARY – JUNE, 2024

**A PUBLICATION OF
GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING AND RESEARCH
BAUCHI STATE,
NIGERIA
07068297660
Support@gamjiinstitute.org**

**This Journal can be cited as:
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities, 1(1)
ISSN:3026-8451**

EDITORIAL BOARD

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Prof. Aminu Ahmad

(Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria)

EDITORS/REVIEWERS

Prof. Bello Ayuba

(Faculty of Management Science, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria)

Samuel Muangi, PhD

(Department of Sociology, Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya)

Ibrahim Alkali

(Department of Sociology, Yobe State University, Yobe, Nigeria)

Prof. Abdullahi Hassan Gorondutse

(Department of Economic and Management Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano, Nigeria)

Jibrin Babayo, PhD

(Department of Sociology, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Auwal Yahaya, PhD

(Department of Economics, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Jamilu Yaya, PhD

(Department of Sociology, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Yahaya Yakubu, PhD

(Department of Economics, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Yusuf Musa Yahaya, PhD

(Department of Political Science, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Auwal Kabir, PhD

(Department of Accounting, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Mohammed Inuwa, PhD

(Department of Business Administration, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Yusuf A. Yusuf, PhD

(Department of Public Administration, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

Ahmad Ahmad Hassan

(Department of Sociology, University of Kashere, Gombe, Nigeria)

Magaji Dafi, PhD

(Department of Social Development, Abubakar Tatari Ali Polytechnic, Bauchi, Nigeria)

Ntongha Eni Ikpi, PhD

(Department of Sociology, University of Calabar, Cross Rivers, Nigeria)

Muktar Mohammed Aliyu, PhD

(Department of English, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria)

CONTENTS

Editorial Note	i
Organisational Politics and Withdrawal Behaviors: A Study of Public Universities in Nigeria	
By Abdulrahman Alkali Gaji, Muhammad Inuwa, Aliyu Ibrahim	1
The Influence of Entrepreneurial Intention On Business Start-Up Intention Among Final Year Students of Bauchi State University: The Mediating Effect of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy	
By Emmanuel Lazarus Boyi, Muhammad Adamu, PhD	23
Appraisal of Peaceful Means of International Dispute Settlement	
By AbdulQadir Al-Ameen, PhD	40
Assessment of Public Policy Implementaton of the Public Procurement Act 2007 In The Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) Abuja, Nigeria	
By Dance, Ayuba Maikasuwa, Sylvanus Muhammed Itodo	70
Crowdfunding as The New Hope for Financing Small Business Entrepreneurship in Nigeria	
By Bukar Ali Bularafa, PhD	93
Effect of Technological Factors on Intention to Adopt Industry 4.0 Technology: The Role of Top Management Support	
By Ya'u Mudasiru Muhammed, Muhammad Adamu, PhD	118
Poverty and Food Insecurity as Disaster in Niger State	
By Umar Baba Ndeji, Mukhtar Iliyasu	149
Impact of Electricity Power Outage on Manufacturing Performance in Nigeria: A Time Series Approach (1985-2022)	
By Balarabe Inuwa Dutse, Mukhtar Iliyasu	160

EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad
Chairman, Editorial Board
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities
Gamji Institute for Training and Research

APPRAISAL OF PEACEFUL MEANS OF INTERNATIONAL DISPUTE SETTLEMENT

By

AbdulQadir Al-Ameen, PhD

Lecturer, Department of Social Sciences, Azman University, Kano, Nigeria

07063544945. abuhananaan3@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12609738

ABSTRACT

Dispute has been a feature of relations between different international entities. People have suffered from the effects of wars in which millions have been killed. Since the dawn of human history until the present time, the world has witnessed a state of continuous disputes that take the form of conflict and violence, and reaches the point of war at times. These disputes often result in tragedies and humanitarian problems for people. Humanity was not able to establish binding rules for settling disputes that were the cause of the outbreak of destructive wars. Throughout history, efforts have been focused on searching for the best ways to resolve disputes peacefully and reduce their effects when they became impossible to prevent. This paper seeks to explore the definition, classification and peaceful means of resolving international disputes known in international relations. Methodologically, the paper used a qualitative method through secondary sources to assess their benefits and weaknesses. The paper argues that international legal jurisprudence is more than clear on the usefulness of peaceful means of international dispute settlement. However, these means are inseparable from weaknesses as well as the cost associated to them. The paper concludes that negotiation is the cheapest and most important diplomatic means that a state can resort to in its relations with other states, as it organizes these relations with the aim of achieving political goals and economic benefits. In addition, it ensures peaceful settlement by managing disputes, conflicts, and wars. It recommends that the rules mentioned in The Hague Conventions should be developed with regards to classification of international disputes

Keywords: Dispute, International dispute settlement, International relations, Peaceful means, UN

1. INTRODUCTION

Settlement of international disputes by peaceful means is one of the behaviors that humans have practiced since ancient times and throughout its long history. These means play a major role in the modern era, as they are the method through which people seek to resolve their differences and conflicts and reach solutions that are satisfactory and acceptable to all parties as an alternative to conflict, wars and confrontations.

Under traditional international law, states resolve disputes that break out among themselves, by resorting to the use of armed force or other coercive means.

With the development of the international community, international law developed steadily, and the use of force to resolve international disputes became prohibited.

Article 2 of the UN Charter lays out the principles under which the UN and its members are required to pursue the aims of Article 1. Article 2 (3) states that all members shall settle their international disputes by peaceful means in such a manner that international peace, security and justice, are not endangered.

Article 33 of the Charter provides that any dispute that is likely to endanger the maintenance of international peace and security should first be addressed through negotiation, mediation or other peaceful means. It also states that the Council can call on the parties to use such means to settle their dispute.

This means that peaceful settlement of dispute is a matter of choice. However, that choice should be in accordance with the dispute itself. Hence, this paper raises the following problems: What are the mechanisms for settling international disputes through Peaceful methods? What are the most important international conventions that address this?

To answer this problem, the paper is structured as follows: definition, types of international disputes and criteria for distinguishing between them, dispute resolution through diplomatic means and dispute resolution through judicial means. Finally, it concluded with a number of findings and recommendations.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Since the area of international dispute settlement is relatively new in the international legal discipline as an academic enterprise, there is still little existing literature about it.

Journal articles such as “Peaceful Settlement of Disputes” by Alicia (2021), “International Dispute Settlement – from Practice to Legal Discipline” by Eric (2018) and “**Dispute Settlement in International Law**” by Loris, & Paolo (2018) first explain the Peaceful settlement of international disputes as a fundamental principle of international law of a peremptory character.

Traditionally, in the field of peaceful settlement of disputes, much of international law scholarship has focused on judicial means for pacific settlement or diplomatic means of settlement separately. Less attention has been devoted to the integration of both binding methods and diplomatic means of settlement.

However, there is debate amongst scholars as to which means is the most effective and important that a state can resort to in its relations with other states, as it organizes these relations with the aim of achieving political goals and economic benefits. Literature such as "International disputes; Study on the peaceful settlement of international disputes and the use of military force in the light of the provisions of international law and their practical application in the Iraqi-Iranian conflict", legal series 11 by Al-Fatlawy (1986) and “International public law” by Abou-Heif (1971) pointed out negotiation as the most important and basic means of settling differences, with some scholars arguing that is nothing as such, and others claiming that it completely depends on scholar’s opinion.

The United Nations Security Council, a United Nations’ organ that promotes more inclusive Pacific Settlement of Disputes, has been the leading source for discussions about pacific means of Settlement of international disputes. The organization's website stipulates in Article 33 under Chapter VI of UN Charter, that mandates states to first address any dispute that is likely to endanger the maintenance of international peace and security through negotiation. This signifies the position and significance of negotiation. Diplomat Magazine, a leading foreign affairs publication that provokes intelligent discussion from the heart of the diplomatic community, has conducted several case studies in an attempt to assess the efficacy of pacific means of Settlement of international disputes. However, it has ultimately concluded that judicial methods have long-lasting effects. There are gaps to fill, Even though scholars are becoming more interested in the area of international dispute settlement as it continues to evolve. This paper seeks to

identify peaceful means for international dispute settlement and the most important international conventions that address them by analyzing their benefits and weaknesses.

2.1 INTERNATIONAL DISPUTE

There are many definitions that address the meaning of dispute, and what concerns us here is the meaning of international dispute, and international law jurists have addressed this in many of their works. International dispute has been defined as contradictory claims between two or more international legal persons (Al-Fatlawy, 1986 p26). It is also defined as disputes that arise between two countries over a legal issue or a specific conflict in their economic, political, or military interests or the difference in their legal arguments regarding them (Al-Attayah, 1987, p. 379). Some authors have defined international dispute as a situation that includes divergence and disagreement in points of view on issues that are often governed by considerations of a legal nature (Fahmy,nd, p. 37.).

The Permanent Court of International Justice (ICJ) in its decision issued on August 3, 1924 in the Mavromets case, defined international conflict as a dispute between two states over a legal issue or a specific incident or due to a conflict between their legal views or interests (Charles Rousseau,1982). In its decision regarding the issue of the right of passage in Indian territory, the same court has defined international conflict as a disagreement on a matter of fact or law, in other words, it is a conflict of legal claims or interests between two people (International Court of Justice, 1957). In summary, based on the definitions we have provided and the events that the international community is experiencing, there may be conflict of interests between states or subjects of international law, and their viewpoints may differ in legal or factual aspects. This dispute and difference must be settled to prevent it from turning into a broader conflict that may lead to war and scourges. For this reason, states and international organizations are keen to lay proper foundations for resolving these disputes in a way that ensures the protection of international peace and security.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

Several methods were adopted to collect data on this topic. Qualitative methods such as; collection and selection of academic literature, scientific journals, and the internet, as well

as a description of the collected materials. Applied methods were used to identify, analyze and evaluate the peaceful means of international dispute settlement in international law.

3. TYPES OF INTERNATIONAL DISPUTES

It goes without saying that sovereignty, borders, and other issues were and still are major causes of international disputes. Ancient empires and peoples made modest attempts to organize dispute issues and resolve them peacefully. In the modern era, the situation is completely different. International jurisprudence and law have begun to precisely define what disputes mean. International disputes are divided according Al-Jaboury (2002) into the following types:

- a) Political disputes.
- b) Legal disputes.
- c) Technical disputes

Some scholars divide international disputes into armed and unarmed disputes. However, I do not agree with this classification because the use of force or not is a characteristic associated to the conflict and not a type of dispute. As for technical disputes, they is a new category that has emerged recently. The emergence of these disputes was an inevitable result of the development of international relations and the tremendous scientific progress in all fields. Over the past few years, many conferences have been held to discuss issues related to technical disputes and to prepare their own agreements. Example is the United Nations conferences on preparing agreements on the production, manufacture and export of rubber and on settling issues related to tin. No matter how many opinions have been expressed regarding the division of international disputes into types, it is a general rule that for a conflict to acquire international character, it must meet certain conditions, and these conditions can be deduced through the opinions that have been said in connection with the definition of international conflict. These opinions are issued by jurists, international bodies and institutes interested in international law. Al Fatlaawy (1986) highlighted the conditions thus:

1. The dispute must be between two or more people according to international law. The dispute may be between two countries, as is the case in the dispute between Britain and Argentina over the Falkland Islands; the dispute between Iraq and Iran over the common border; the dispute between Britain and Spain over Gibraltar; and the dispute between India and Pakistan. The dispute may be between a state and an international organization as is the case of Kashmir. Other examples include the dispute between Egypt and the World Health Organization in 1980 regarding the interpretation of the treaty concluded between the two parties in 1951 and the dispute that recently erupted between the International Atomic Energy Agency and North Korea. This dispute is due to the latter's resumption of its nuclear program, which the agency considered a violation of the agreement that North Korea had previously signed with it, which included subjecting its nuclear facilities to international supervision. The agency subsequently decided to raise the issue before the UN Security Council on 2/12/2003. The conflict may also be between a state and a recognized national liberation movement
2. That there are contradictory claims between the parties to the conflict that need to be settled, but the difference in viewpoints cannot be considered an international dispute because this difference does not entail rights for either party, and thus it is not considered an international dispute. The positions of both the United States of America and the former Soviet Union regarding the Palestinian issue differ. The same can be said about the differing positions of the United States and Russia on the same issue.
3. That the contradictory claims are continuous. When a state claims a certain right towards another state and the latter in turn rejects this right and the matter ends there, a situation of international conflict does not arise because the first state did not want to follow up on what it claimed of the right. There may also be outstanding problems between two countries without being accompanied by allegations against each other, meaning that each of the two countries avoids causing problems for certain reasons. In this case, an international conflict does not also arise.

4. The dispute must be able to be settled in accordance with the rules of settling international disputes. However, if it is not possible to settle it, it is not considered an international dispute, meaning that its settlement results in one or both of the disputing parties doing something or abstaining from it. It is not considered an international dispute if one country disagrees with another in political or national ideologies despite the fact that those countries are enthusiastic about their positions and their claim that what they adopt is the best. It does not amount to an international dispute due to the impossibility of resolving this difference according to the rules of settling international disputes.

4. CRITERIA FOR DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN TYPES OF INTERNATIONAL DISPUTES

The opinions of jurists have varied regarding the distinction between the two main types of international disputes: legal disputes and political disputes. Disagreements arose between jurists in their attempt to set dividing lines between these two types of dispute. In this regard, the jurisprudence can be divided into two main trends.

The first trend: The proponents of this trend take an objective point of view, and Gold Schmidt believes that legal disputes are those that by their nature allow a ruling based on the rules of law (a judicial decision), while illegal disputes are those that do not, by their nature, allow a ruling based on the rules of the law. The professor (Devissher) adds: the adoption of this standard, i.e. the objective one, is an issue that varies according to the specialty of the researcher or jurist. He believes that a legal dispute is that which can be settled on the basis of the principles of the law. In contrast, politicians see that the link between the dispute and the interests of the state is the decisive issue in the matter. Whenever this link is strong, i.e. the dispute is related to the highest interests of the state, such as national or economic interests, then the dispute is considered a political dispute. If however the association is not like that, i.e. the dispute relates to secondary or small issues and does not affect the higher interests of the state, then the dispute is considered legal. The supporters of this trend are both Briggs and Giraud.

The second trend: The proponents of this trend, led by Professor Kastberg, take a personal standard and believe that the way the parties present the issue in dispute is the

decisive factor in determining whether the dispute is of a legal or political nature. The dispute is legal as long as the parties do not dispute over the application of the rules of International law or its interpretation. The David Davies Institute for International Studies in London is also inclined to the personal point of view. The dispute may be political, but if both parties demand their legal rights, the dispute is clearly a legal dispute. In other words, the legal dispute is that which the dispute focuses on the application of an existing law or its interpretation. As for the political conflict, the dispute focuses on one party's demand to amend the existing law, as is the case in the German-Polish dispute regarding the Danzig Corridor in 1939 (Al-Jaboury).

It must be pointed out that there is an opinion in jurisprudence that goes towards searching for the will of the parties to the conflict. If it is to resolve the dispute according to the law, the dispute is legal, otherwise they are facing a political dispute. Another opinion is that if the dispute responds to a private interest, it is a political dispute, but if it responds to a right, it is a legal dispute (**Gerhard .1970**). The Hague Agreements of 1899 and 1907, the League of Nations and the Statute of the International Court of Justice all came to put an end to the dispute over what disputes are considered legal and what are not. These agreements and charters provided a clear enumeration of legal disputes, and therefore everything that was not mentioned is not considered legal but rather falls under the category of political or technical disputes.

5. DIPLOMATIC MEANS

5.1 DIRECT NEGOTIATIONS

Direct negotiations are the most used and ubiquitous mechanism for dispute settlement. They should be the first step in the resolution of any dispute. They can be obligatory or optional. The parties usually will try to solve their dispute by direct negotiations and if the negotiations fail, they will resort to another mechanism for dispute settlement. Negotiations and the duty to negotiate have their origin in customary international law, conventional law and are also recognized in the general customary law. One of the characteristics of negotiation is that it can be done at different levels: between administrative agencies and experts, ministries of foreign affairs, diplomats or even at a

summit or a conference. However, the most common level is between ministries of foreign affairs.

The success of direct negotiations depends on the determination, goodwill and readiness of the participants to reach a compromise or an agreement. Furthermore, maintaining secrecy and keeping the negotiation away from the public and the media is important element in order to make a compromise and overcome obstacles. Publicity and the media coverage of negotiations may make them impossible, because the pressure and demands coming from the public, and especially the public opinion, sometimes can be very difficult to avoid (Lapidoth, pp.12-13).

The exhaustion of negotiation is a precondition for the resort to other means of dispute settlement. In many cases, it is complicated to detect if and when negotiation has been exhausted. There are also cases where a party refuses to negotiate, regardless of its obligation to do so. Such a refusal may be a consequence of a very bad mutual relations (like the relations between Iran and the USA in 1979-1980, at the time of hostage crisis) or a lack of recognition (like the non-recognition of Israel by the Arab States in the past).

There are a number of conditions required before the beginning of every negotiation. The first requirement is the existence of recognizable parties – two or more. The next requirement involves a subject of mutual interest for the parties, i.e. a dispute that is negotiable, motivation to negotiate, a desire and need among the parties to reach an agreement, a strong will to find a quick solution for their dispute strengthened with a deadline, and an applicable and appropriate agreement.

The process of negotiation can be divided into four phases: pre-negotiation, conceptualization, bargaining and settlement. The first phase covers the issues of identification of the parties, detection of mutual interests and selection of a forum for communication. The next phase identifies the positions of each of the parties and the subject matter of the dispute. The third phase is called 'bargaining phase'. In this phase, the parties discuss their positions and negotiate the terms and conditions which will lead to a solution. The final phase is the phase of reaching an agreement.

The benefits and advantages of negotiations includes: lower cost, rapid dispute resolution, direct communication between the representatives of the parties, flexibility

and confidentiality of the process. Negotiations can be more productive compared to other peaceful means for dispute settlement because the parties are familiar with the subject matter of their dispute and any additional disagreements between them can be easily recognized and solved (Strutt, 2014, pp.1-3).

It is absurd that the strongest benefits can induce the greatest disadvantages and weaknesses of direct negotiations. For instance, although speed and flexibility are considered as advantages they can easily undermine the negotiation process. The flexibility can be abused by one party to harm the other. This is the case when in the absence of regulation, the natural power of one of the parties prevails and the party can influence the settlement of the dispute. Speed, on the other hand, can lead to unbalanced settlement and resentment on the side of one of the parties.

Negotiations do not necessarily end with an agreement, although that is the aim. Among the disadvantages of negotiation is the possibility to last endlessly, in order to cover the failure of resolving the dispute: not resolving it is “better” than admitting the failure of negotiations. However, if there is a will on the side of the parties, it can be conducted fast and flexible. Moreover, during the negotiation, the parties must manifest their ‘good faith’ for reaching a settlement. The term ‘good faith’ is also flexible and it may have different meanings in different circumstances depending on the dispute. In addition to the different features of negotiation, it is worth mentioning the distinction between bilateral and multilateral negotiations, in particular, on the issue of the dynamics, which can play a major role in the case of multilateral negotiations (Palmer, 2012, pp. 41-42).

An example of a successful negotiation is the case connected to NATO air attacks (Operation Allied Force) against Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (FRY or Serbia today). The Embassy of People’s Republic of China in Belgrade, the capital city of FRY, was an accidental target of an air strike on 7th of May 1999. The USA officially stated that the bombing was accidental and a “tragic mistake”. According to the US government, the main intention had been to bomb the nearby Directorate for Supply and Procurement of FRY and that Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) had identified the wrong coordinates for Yugoslav military target on the same street. CIA Director, George Tenet further testified before a Congressional Committee that this air attack was the only one in the operation that was organized and directed by the CIA. According to the statement from the Chinese

government, the bombing was a 'barbarian act'. The negotiations between USA and China led to a Memorandum of understanding signed on the 30th of July 1999. The USA agreed to pay a compensation of 4.5 million US dollars to China for the families of those who lost their lives or sustained injuries in the bombing. The USA and China signed two compensation agreements on the 16th of December 1999 about the material damage caused to the diplomatic property on both sides. In the first agreement, the USA agreed to pay a compensation of 28 million US dollars for the damage caused to the Chinese Embassy in Belgrade. With the second agreement, China agreed to pay 2.87 million US dollars as a compensation for the damage caused to the US diplomatic and consular properties in China, caused by Chinese protesters (Murphy, pp.99-102).

The negotiations ended when the disputing parties reached a compromise or an agreement. Although negotiation do not imply an obligation for the parties to reach an agreement. In a situation where the negotiation is not successful and the dispute threatens the international peace and security, article 33 of the UN Charter recommends that parties need to continue with other means for peaceful settlement of disputes, usually called good offices.

5.2 GOOD OFFICES

'Good offices' as a mechanism for dispute solution differs from negotiation because it involves an intervention of a third entity/party who is not a party to the dispute. The third party can be involved on the initiative of both parties to the dispute. When direct negotiations reach the point where no progress is possible, especially because of fundamental disagreement between the opposing parties, the 'good offices' can be applied. As a term, it has two meanings which are different but closely related. The first meaning describes the third party as a subject who will encourage the parties to resume the direct negotiations. The second meaning include both mediation and 'good offices'. It is connected with any non-structured form of support given by a third party. However, there is a difference between mediation and 'good offices'. The third party in the 'good offices' has a passive role and tends to bring the parties to negotiations again. This means that the third entity communicates with both of the parties separately and does not

participate in the resolution of the dispute, because the final decision about this issue is on the parties. On the other hand, the mediator has an active role in the process, offering suggestions and proposals for resolution of the dispute.

One of the main characteristics of this mechanism is the necessary mutual consent of both parties. If the parties of the dispute cannot reach agreement by direct negotiation, they may jointly seek the good offices by a third party, but it does not mean that there is an obligation for the parties to submit their dispute to this method (Lapidoth, p.14). The third party can be represented by a state, international organization (United Nations), or a prominent person, such as the UN Secretary-General. The third party must be neutral, impartial and trustworthy, with an ability to restore the favorable atmosphere between the parties.

An example of successful 'good offices' is the peace agreement between Russia and Japan, signed on the 5th of September 1905. The US President Theodore Roosevelt had a role of a third party in the 'good offices' in this case. The Nobel Peace Prize in 1906 was awarded to Roosevelt for having negotiated peace in the Russo-Japanese war in 1904-1905 and for his contribution towards resolving the dispute with Mexico by resorting to the Permanent Court of Arbitration in 1902 for the case USA vs. Mexico (Pious Fund of the California's case).

The dispute about the name issue between Greece and Macedonia is another example of 'good offices'. It began with the application of the Republic of Macedonia for UN membership. After examining the application of the Republic of Macedonia, the UN Security Council adopted Resolution 817 on 7th of April 1993. The Security Council noted the differences over the name of the state (Republic of Macedonia) and recommended to the UN General Assembly the admission by the provisional reference "the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia" until the settlement of the name dispute with Greece. The Security Council welcomed the Co-Chairmen of the Steering Committee of the International Conference on the Former Yugoslavia (Cyrus Vance and Lord David Owen) to settle the dispute. Consequently, the 'good offices' turned into mediation. The UN Secretary-General appointed a special representative Cyrus Vance as a mediator, who was replaced with Matthew Nimetz in December 1999.

The 'good offices' can be finished in two possible ways: when the parties resume the direct negotiations or when the third party does not succeed to create a positive ambience and communication between the opposing parties hindering the resumption of the negotiation.

4.3. MEDIATION

Mediation is the second most used peaceful means for dispute settlement after direct negotiation. It involves a third party - mediator who attempts to settle a dispute. It is defined as a non-binding, but flexible, voluntary and confidential process in which the third neutral party actively assists in settlement of the dispute.

The key figure in mediation is the mediator. A mediator is an active participant in the process of dispute settlement between the opposing parties and he offers assistance, guidance and help to both parties, in order to understand all important points of their dispute. Mediation can be performed by representatives of a state or an NGO, by an international organization or its functionaries, such as the Secretary-General of the UN and its representative, or by respected and distinguished persons. Although designation of a distinguished personality is more common, the representative of a powerful state or international organization has more chances for success due to the ability of the powerful state to influence the parties and their behavior. A person can be designated for mediator only by consent of the parties. Mediation can also be initiated by one of the parties or even by the mediator himself/herself (Bernier and Latulippe, p.4). In practice, it is difficult to find such a person or a state who would willingly agree to mediate, since this mechanism is a difficult assignment which requires patience and proficiency. Accordingly, not all mediations achieve to end the dispute.

The duty of a mediator is to clarify the position of each party, improve ambience and make proposals for a solution of the dispute. As a figure, he/she is characterized with objectivity, neutrality, discretion, impartiality and independence. His/her major duty is to discreetly transmit the proposals of one party to the other, on separate meetings. For that reason, the mediator has a very important role in making the process much easier for the parties, especially in a situation when the relations between the parties reached an impasse: in such a case the mediator will continue to work with each party separately,

until a compromise is reached. The mediator is interested in bringing the dispute to an end, because it demonstrates his/her success (Lapidoth, p.15).

The role of the mediator is to create a positive atmosphere in which the parties can communicate, to assist in breaking impasses and to prevent direct confrontation between the parties. For these reasons, the mediation is often called 'assisted negotiation'.

The process of mediation can also be explained as a communication assisted by a third party. There are many ways to accomplish the communication between the parties: they can communicate directly between each other; the mediator can assist their communication; or the mediator can communicate with them separately.

The contemporary form of mediation is more formal compared to negotiation. The formality is corroborated with the acceptance by institutional bodies who are concerned with the vigorous process and the rules and regulations of mediation.

Among the most common advantages of mediation is the flexibility, the necessity of consent, the inexpensive procedure, the opportunity of the parties to have control over the process and the resolution of their dispute.

The flexibility is usually restricted by the will and readiness of the parties to cooperate with the support from the mediator. It can be also reflected in the speed of solving the disputes.

The consent of the parties is necessary at all points of the mediation in order to lead to successful dispute resolution. In many cases, the consent can be the basis for agreement between the parties.

The cost is under direct control of the parties. Their wish for quick settlement of the dispute and the level of cooperation with the mediator, can lead to small costs for the parties (Keith, p.4).

Although the low cost was mentioned as one of the advantages of mediation, it can also be a disadvantage. Normally, mediation is not cheap: it is much more cost effective compared to other means, but only if it succeeds in the dispute settlement. If it fails, the final resolution of the dispute will be delayed and it will lead to waste of resources.

Another disadvantage is the consensual nature of mediation, which can cause failure of the mediation even with the assistance of the mediator. The vulnerability of the process may be increased by the parties with the misuse of mediation and their aspiration to delay the settlement of the dispute.

The non-binding character of the opinions and suggestions of the mediator is also a disadvantage. However, when parties achieve the settlement, the agreement between them needs to be enforced (Keith, p.4).

One of the characteristics of mediation is the consent of all parties. There must be prior commitment. All parties have to agree to the mediation. Additionally, the services offered by the mediator are not obligatory for the parties - they can either accept or reject them, but they usually agree to mediation if they are looking for a compromise (Keith, p.5).

The successful end of mediation depends on timing. In many cases, the mediator enters the scene in a period when the parties are already exhausted of the war or after unsuccessful attempts to solve their disputes.

In order to solve the dispute successfully, mediation also needs confidentiality.

The parties to the dispute are often facing difficulties to find a person or a state who would agree to take the role of a mediator since mediation is a very complex mission which requires a lot of time and tolerance and at the end cannot guarantee success. Cautious selection of the mediator can also facilitate the differences between the parties, particularly the cultural one. The aim of the mediation is to assist the communication between the opposing parties and to help them to avoid any future misunderstanding.

As one of the most used peaceful means for dispute settlement, mediation is flexible and it is not restrained by legal structures. However, it is still difficult to find an acceptable mediator for a dispute. Mediation as a technique is considered to have active involvement of a third party, which will make an attempt to help the parties to settle their dispute and reach an agreement. Mediators may use different ways to persuade the parties: they can encourage them to find a rational reason to make approach to the other party; they help them to see the weaknesses and strengths of their approaches or positions; and to introduce a sense of fairness and honesty between them (Palmer, 2012, p. 42).

Compared to arbitrators, the role of mediators is much more active and intrusive. Mediators identify the fundamental interests and positions of the parties on joint, but also separate and confidential meetings. This kind of proactive involvement of the mediator can contribute to the success of the mediation (Bernier and Latulippe, p.4). Different mediators have different styles and different skills. Their role is not a role of a judge, but they need to be critical in the process of facilitating and guiding the parties to reach a settlement (Brennan, 2015, pp.145-146).

An example of effective mediation is the conflict between Chile and Argentina about the Beagle Channel. The Beagle conflict was a border dispute over the possession of Lennox, Piston and Nueva islands and the scope of maritime jurisdiction related with those islands that brought Chile and Argentina to the edge of war in 1978. The conflict began in 1904 with the first official Argentine claims over the islands that had always been under Chilean control. The Pope, John Paul II was the mediator in this case which was resolved in 1984 when Argentina recognized the islands as Chilean territory. The Pope had two proposals: the first one from 1980 was accepted by Chile and rejected by Argentina, and the second one from 1984 was a subject of referendum in Argentina, which produced a result of 82.6% in favor of the papal proposal. Both parties then accepted the mediation of Vatican in 1979 with the Act of Montevideo and after 5 years, in 1984, they signed the Treaty of Peace and Friendship at Vatican City giving the islands to Chile and maritime jurisdiction to Argentina.

Other examples of successful mediation include: the mediation of the Soviet Union in the dispute between India and Pakistan in 1966 and the mediation of Algeria in the dispute between USA and Iran regarding the hostage crisis in 1980-1981. In this case, Algeria as a mediator suggested to Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini to make “a gesture of goodwill” towards Algeria as a third party, and not towards the USA.

Mediation ends when the dispute is solved in accordance with the proposals of the mediator and the parties reach an agreement or when all suggested proposals are not accepted by the parties and the dispute is not solved.

4.4 INQUIRY (COMMISSION OF INQUIRY)

4.5 Inquiry is similar to ‘good offices’ and can be used in two related, but different connotations. The first connotation includes disputes between states created by disagreements over facts and a third party with a task to solve those disputes. The second meaning of the term ‘inquiry’ is related to a specific institutional arrangement or settlement which needs to clarify only a specific point of fact. In the practice of the international law, the term ‘enquiry’ is used as an equivalent of the term ‘inquiry’. Geoffrey Palmer attempted to distinguish these two similar terms. He recalled the distinction made in the New Zealand Oxford Dictionary of 2005. According to the explanation given in it, there is a useful distinction between these terms, although they are used alternatively. The term enquire means ‘to ask something’, in general context, while inquire means ‘to make a formal investigation’. Although the international practice is variable, the same distinction refers to terms ‘inquiry’ and ‘enquiry’.

The main purpose of the inquiry is to facilitate the solution of the dispute that occur from the difference of opinion *on facts* by clarifying these facts. For that reason, the inquiry is also known by the term ‘fact-finding’ and commission of inquiry as ‘fact-finding commission’ (Peters, 2003, p.5).

This mechanism was established as a ‘Commission of inquiry’ in 1899 and 1907 by The Hague Conventions for the Pacific Settlement of International Disputes. The latter convention has introduced the functioning and the procedure for the establishment of the commission of inquiry. This technique is based on the hypothesis that if an authoritative and respected third party solves the disagreement, then the dispute solution is obvious. One of the characteristics of the inquiry is the role of the commission in clarifying the facts or the factual question of the case. The commission does not explain or resolve the question of legality.

The procedure established by the 1907 Hague Convention proved to be successful, but it has been used in a very small number of cases. It was replaced with other *ad hoc* fact-finding techniques used by international organizations, such as the United Nations, formally the League of Nations and some of its specialized agencies like the International

Labour Organization). Fact-finding has been included in the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, within the context of 'special arbitration' as one of the means that member states can choose.

This mechanism was rarely used in practice. In fact, the inquiry was used in few cases only: Dogger Bank in 1904, Tavignano case in 1912, Tiger case in 1918, Tubantia case in 1922 and Red Crusader in 1961.

The necessity for impartial investigation of the facts of the dispute was obvious in the period of events that led to the Spanish-American war in 1898. Hostilities began in February 1898 in the aftermath of the internal explosion of the USS Maine (ACR-1) - the American naval battleship - that sank in Cuba's Havana harbor during the Cuban revolt against Spain. The ship was destroyed by a massive explosion that led to deaths of 250 out of 355 American crew members aboard. Apparently on a friendly visit, the Maine had been sent to Cuba to protect the interests of American citizens after a rebellion against Spanish in Havana in January 1898. Most American leaders, including the US president William McKinley, declared that the cause of the explosion was unknown, but the American public opinion blamed Spain for the explosion. In order to solve the case, they formed two commissions for investigation. The US investigation by an official US Navy Court of inquiry concluded that the ship was destroyed by an external explosion caused by a mine that was set off under the ship's hull. However, Spain's investigation came to opposite conclusion that the explosion was linked with factors within the ship. These different reports about the cause of the explosion made the war inevitable. Almost 80 years later (in 1976), a team of American naval investigators concluded that the explosion was not caused by Spanish mine or sabotage, but by a fire that ignited its ammunition stocks. However, there were different conclusions about how the forward magazines could have exploded.

The function of the Commission of inquiry is to investigate the facts of the dispute and set them out in a report. The Commission may be appointed by consent (agreement) between the parties of the dispute. The most famous case including inquiry is "Dogger Bank case" between United Kingdom and Russia. The case was about the attacks by Russian warships on British fishing vessels in the North Sea in October 1904. The Russian warships were engaged in the war with Japan and attacked the British fishing trawlers because they

thought they were Japanese torpedo boats (Palmer, 2012, p.42). The Dogger Bank incident almost led to war between Russia and Britain. The incident was dangerous due to Anglo-Japanese alliance. The Russian and the British governments signed a joint agreement in November 1904 in which they agreed to submit the case to an international commission of inquiry. In 1905 Russia voluntarily paid a compensation of 66,000 British pounds to the fishermen.

Another well-known case is the so-called Red Crusader case from 1961. It is about an incident that occurred in May 1961 between British fishing vessel and Danish gunboat. The commission of inquiry in its report concluded that Danish frigate “Niels Ebbesen” exceeded the legitimate use of armed force by firing without warning and creating a danger to human life on board the Aberden trawler Red Crusader. Although the inquiry does not aim to solve the dispute, but only to explain the facts of the dispute, the Red Crusader was the only case in which the commission of inquiry gives legal considerations and qualifications (about the legitimate use of armed force).

Inquiry is rarely used as an exclusive mechanism for dispute settlement, but it is more often used as a part or an addition to other mechanisms.

The ‘commission of inquiry’ as a fact-finding commission can be a successful mechanism for dispute settlement only if the cause of disagreement is related to facts, and parties are motivated to accept the reality that their own version of the events may be incorrect.

The finding of the inquiry has non-binding nature, except in a situation where the parties has previously agreed the contrary.

4.6 CONCILIATION (CONCILIATION COMMISSION)

Conciliation as a mechanism has been established in the 1920s with the General Act for the pacific settlement of international disputes from 1928. Usually, it includes institutionalized and impartial commissions which investigate disputes and recommend possible solutions for settlement. Each of the parties specifies acceptance or rejection of the commission's proposal. If the parties accept the proposal, the commission drafts an agreement, called *procés verbal*, which includes the conditions of the settlement. Although the commission’s proposals are non-binding, there is an obligation for certain disputes to be submitted to conciliation.

The difference between this commission and the commission of inquiry is in the subject of investigation. The duties of the commission of conciliation are not limited only to clarifying the questions of fact. Moreover, conciliation can be very similar to mediation, because the conciliator can act as a mediator in convincing the parties to accept certain solution.

Among other features typical for conciliation is the possibility to use it in combination with other diplomatic means, as an additional mechanism. The commission can be established as a permanent commission or on *ad hoc* basis and its proceedings are confidential. The type of decisions the commission will arrive at depends on various factors, such as the attitude of the opposing parties, the contents of the instrument that created the commission, the perception of the conciliators about their function, etc. For that reason, in some cases, the procedure can be of a cooperative character and in others it can be more formal and can include pleadings by the opposing parties.

The procedure starts with the submission of the dispute to the commission upon the request of one party. The fact-finding commission is a combination of an inquiry commission and a conciliation commission. It consists of an odd number of members selected by each of the parties and a third member chosen by the two already appointed members. The important feature is the third person who may not have the nationality of either party and will take the position of a chairman. If the parties fail to agree on a chairman within three months starting from the request for the establishment of the commission, the power will shift to the Secretary-General of the UN. It is also possible for one of the parties to refuse appointing its own member and this can be connected with a situation in which one of the parties wants to avoid previously committed arbitration. However, once the commission is formed, it will establish its procedure and the parties have to ensure that any information required by the commission is provided. The procedure ends with adoption of a report (by a majority vote) and its submission to the parties. The report includes the commission's findings and recommendations for reasonable and impartial solution of the dispute. These recommendations do not have to be in accordance with any legal framework and the parties do not have an obligation to adopt and implement the report, but to consider it "in good faith".

The references “findings” and “recommendations” are similar to other two peaceful means: conciliation and inquiry. Hence, the “findings” point in the direction of commission of inquiry and the “recommendations” can be connected to conciliation. The Vienna Convention on the Law of the Treaties and the Vienna Convention on Succession of States in Respect of Treaties provide conciliation as a technique for dispute settlement. The main aim of this technique is to assist friendly settlement. The role of the Conciliation Commission is to examine the objections and claims, to hear the parties, and to make proposals for resolution of their dispute. The final and recommendatory award of the Conciliation Commission must be considered by the parties in ‘good faith’ (Palmer, 2012, p.43). Conciliation is similar to arbitration concerning neutrality and the impartial role of the Conciliation Commission, which is necessary in order to obtain the trust of the parties. In other aspects, conciliation is also similar to mediation. In practice, conciliation is a precondition for submitting a case in front of arbitration. It is not intended to determine who is right or wrong and it plays an active role in examining the dispute. The proposal for settlement is not necessarily based on law and is not binding for the parties (Bernier and Latulippe, p.6).

Conciliation appeared after the World War I in the Locarno Treaties of 1925 and the General Act of Arbitration of 1928. The aim of the conciliation was to find a common position between the parties and to propose a non-binding solution. Due to its impartial character, conciliation was explained more as a legal and formal mechanism.

Like inquiry, conciliation, was in fact, applied in few cases. Conciliation in practice included issues regarding violations of national sovereignty, existence of rights and privileges, compensation for injury to foreign nationals or violation of their vested interests, and interpretation of bilateral treaties (Bernier and Latulippe, p.9). As a mechanism, conciliation was used in the territorial dispute between Guatemala and Belize, instituted by the Organization of American States (OAS) in 2002. The report of the conciliation commission is significant by itself, because the OAS made efforts to encourage the parties to see beyond their dispute in order to reach a solution based on mutual respect and cooperation.

An interesting example is the conciliation between Finland and Norway in 1980 regarding the boundaries of the continental shelf in the Jan Mayen sector (a Norwegian volcanic

island situated in the North Arctic Ocean). The report of the conciliation commission included recommendations which were accepted by the parties and led to an agreement in October 1981 (Bernier and Latulippe, p.14).

6. JUDICIAL MEANS

The judicial means for dispute settlement is represented by two essential means: arbitration and proceedings in a court of law. Compared to non-binding effect of reports and conclusions typical for diplomatic means, the effect of an arbitral award and court decision is of a binding character.

Inside the division of the judicial means, there is difference between these two procedures. Court of law, its composition, internal structure, procedure, and the law that will be applied in the case are elements that are previously determined by the Statute of the court and they apply to all cases brought before that court. However, in the case of arbitration, these elements are determined by the parties in the arbitration agreement called 'compromise'. The intention of both procedures is to solve disputes on the basis of law, but arbitrators can take into consideration all relevant elements and circumstances as well. For that reason, arbitration is often characterized as a quasi-judicial procedure (Simmonds, 1987, pp.149-155).

Nonetheless, there is another difference between the jurisdiction of the court in international and domestic law. In domestic laws, courts of law have compulsory jurisdiction, while arbitration is voluntary and requires the consent of the parties. On the other hand, in international law, the jurisdiction of courts and arbitration depends on the consent of the opposing parties.

6.1. Arbitration

Arbitration is recognized as one of the oldest institutions of international law. There is a well-known statement that 'arbitration is only as good as the arbitrators.

There are no codified rules guiding its operation, mainly because the parties create the rules by themselves. However, different organizations (such as United Nations) and its bodies (for instance, the General Assembly or some of the specialized agencies of the UN) have formulated model rules that parties can use for settlement of their dispute. The

parties of the dispute can incorporate these model rules into the agreement called 'compromise' or may include a reference to any set of model rules.

The 'compromise' itself often includes provisions regarding structure of the tribunal, the process of selection of arbiters and their competencies, procedural issues, the rules that will be applied in the case, and the subject matter.

If a party is not satisfied with the arbitral award, it may challenge it on the grounds of exceeding the powers of the tribunal, corruption on the part of the tribunal or arbiter, severe departure from the procedure or rules, and the nullity of the compromise or the possibility to take the dispute before arbitration.

Fraud and error are two additional factors that may also weaken the validity of the arbitral awards. For instance, the non-disclosure clause in the agreement can be an example of fraud. Errors can be divided into two main categories: errors in the interpretation or application of law and errors of fact. The latter category is linked to fact based on evidence and if it is detected after the end of the procedure it can be corrected by revision. The other type of errors – errors in the interpretation or application of the law can be considered only if they represent 'obvious' or 'essential' errors.

As mentioned above, the parties agree on the rules themselves and include those rules in the 'compromise'. In some cases, the parties formulate the rules by themselves and in other cases, the parties refer to the rules of international law. This is also the case whenever the 'compromise' does not include a set of previously agreed rules. In that situation, it can be generally assumed that the rules of international law will be applied.

Other features of arbitration include: the opportunity given to the parties to choose the composition of the arbitration tribunal and to select the arbitrators. The parties can appoint them by name or they can create a procedure for their appointment. The number of arbitrators must be uneven; in most cases it consists of three members. Each party appoints its own arbitrator and both of them agree on the 'neutral' one. If the common agreement cannot be reached between the parties, then a third party, usually the president of the International Court of Justice would be authorized to appoint the 'neutral' arbitrator or the chairman. The member of the arbitral tribunal may not be a national or a habitual resident of any of the parties (Lapidoth, pp. 24-26).

A dispute can be submitted for arbitration with or without the consent of both parties or unilaterally by one of the parties. The parties need to agree on the subject matter of their dispute, and in a case they do not agree on this question, the tribunal will determine it.

At the request of the parties, the arbitral tribunal may suggest 'interim measures' of protection which are not mandatory. The arbitrators and the parties must protect the confidentiality of any information they received in the proceedings. Both parties bear the expenses for the procedure in equal parts.

Although there is no opportunity for a third party to interfere in arbitration, if the tribunal agrees the third party that has a legal interest in the subject matter may interfere in the process.

The process ends with an award which includes the reasons on which it is based. Any of the arbitrators may add individual or dissenting opinion (Lapidoth, p.27). The appellate procedure is allowed only if the parties agreed on it previously. Otherwise there is no possibility to appeal against the arbitral award.

The arbitrators are considered as a type of judges. Parties have the duty to appoint them, but they do not make decisions upon the parties' orders. It is a formal method with a binding effect, and for that reason, as a method of adjudication, it is usually seen as one that applies the law. The parties will prefer the arbitration, as a more attractive method, rather than adjudication in a court of law, because of its flexibility, the privacy of the proceedings, the opportunity for the parties to formulate the subject matter and the procedure. Over the years, a great number of arbitrations at international level has been performed and a great amount of international law regarding them (Palmer, 2012, p.43).

6.2. International Court of Justice

The International Court of Justice (further in the text: ICJ or the Court) is a descendant of the Permanent Court of Justice that was a judicial organ of the League of Nations. After the Second World War, and the establishment of the United Nations in 1945, this court was replaced by the International Court of Justice. All member states of the UN are automatically parties of the Statute of the ICJ, but its jurisdiction is not mandatory for them. In many cases, the decision about the jurisdiction of the ICJ is up to the Court itself. The ICJ consists of 15 judges, elected for nine years.

The Court adjudicates only disputes between States, because only States may be parties in cases before the ICJ. It represents the apex of the dispute settlement pyramid (Rosenne, 2006).

The Statute of ICJ, as a founding Act of the Court, in Article 38 specifies a list of main sources of international law that can be applied by the Court in its jurisdiction. The main sources are: customs, international conventions, and the general principles of law recognized by the civilized nations. There are two additional sources of law that are not enumerated in the Article 38 of the Statute of ICJ, but may be applied by the court: certain resolutions of international organizations and principles of equity or justice (to decide a case *ex aequo et bono*). The principle '*ex aequo et bono*' means in accordance with justice and regardless of the law. So far, there has not been such a case, which proves that states would choose arbitration or some other mechanism for settlement of their dispute if they seek a decision irrespective of the law.

After the written and oral phase of the procedure, the judges decide the case by a majority of the present judges. Although the judgments have to be implemented by the parties, they are not binding as precedents for other cases. There is also a possibility for revision of a judgment if a fact is discovered afterwards and it was not known to the party that requests the revision and to the Court.

The jurisdiction of the ICJ is consensual and the parties have no obligation to accept its compulsory jurisdiction. In 1945, when the United Nations was founded, Australia and New Zealand insisted on compulsory jurisdiction of the ICJ in respect of all members, but their attempt was unsuccessful due to the opinions of the great powers. The United Kingdom is the only member state of all five permanent members of the Security Council that accepted the compulsory jurisdiction of the Court. Other permanent members of the Security Council have different stories behind their refusal. For instance, the acceptance of the Court's compulsory jurisdiction was terminated by France in the beginning of the Nuclear Tests Case (Australia vs. France and New Zealand vs. France in 1973/1974). The United States of America terminated the acceptance of the jurisdiction as a consequence of the Court decision in the case Nicaragua vs. United States of America in 1986 (the case was about military and paramilitary activities in and against Nicaragua, in particular the laying of mines in ports of Nicaragua). Other two permanent members of the Security

Council, China and Russia, have never accepted the compulsory jurisdiction – either by special agreement or under the optional clause (Palmer, 2012, pp. 44-45).

Whenever a State as a party of a dispute addresses the ICJ, it indicates that all other instances or methods are exhausted. Another opinion is that once a dispute comes to the ICJ, there is no longer place for diplomats, but for judges only. Both views do not reflect the reality, because there are cases in which the ICJ is seized without the exhaustion of other peaceful means, particularly negotiations. There are also cases in which the parties did not make any attempt to solve the dispute by other peaceful means. On the other hand, other peaceful means may be used after the institution of proceedings, considering usage of extra judicial means due to achieving the settlement during the case (Kohen, 2013, p.13).

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the presentation of the study, it is clear to us that negotiation is the most important diplomatic means that a state can resort to in its relations with other states, as it organizes these relations with the aim of achieving political goals and economic benefits, in addition to its major role in managing disputes, conflicts, and wars in reaching settlement. On this basis, we find that negotiation as a philosophy, art, and politics is fundamentally linked to achieving peace because it pushes countries to the necessity of reaching an agreement that guarantees the advancement of common interests and extending them to multiple areas that may include all aspects of human life. This is in addition to its major role in consolidating the culture of international security - especially if the seriousness of countries in this field has become clear - because it works to narrow or perhaps end the differences and disputes that may occur between countries as a result of conflicting goals. Thus, it is considered the best way for the parties to achieve their interests in the international environment. In view of this, the paper recommends the following

- 1- Studying the causes of disputes, and developing appropriate techniques and approach for dispute settlement.
- 2- The classification of international disputes, the rules mentioned in the Hague Conventions should be developed.

3- The necessity of organizing the procedures for conducting negotiations with legal texts and rules.

REFERENCE LIST

Al-Attayah Issam .(1987) . Public International Law, 4th edition.

Bernier, Ivan and Latulippe, Nathalie. The International Convention on the protection and promotion of the diversity of cultural expressions: Conciliation as a dispute resolution method in the cultural sector. Available at: http://www.diversite-culturelle.gc.ca/fileadmin/documents/pdf/document_reflexion_eng.pdf [accessed 30th November 2023]

Brennan, Lorraine M.(2015). *Preparing the client in an international mediation: what to expect from the process*. In: Rovine, Arthur W., Contemporary issues in international arbitration and mediation: The Fordham papers. Koninklijke Brill NV, Leiden, The Netherlands.

Charter of the United Nations.(1945). Available at: <http://www.un.org/en/sections/un-charter/un-charter-full-text/> [accessed: 10th December 2013]

Collection of Judgments of the International Court of Justice 1957, pp. 125-149.

French, Duncan, Saul, Mathew and White, Nigel.(2010). (eds.). International law and dispute settlement: New problems and techniques, Hart Publishing, Oxford.

Gerhard Vinglhan. (1970). Law among Nations introduction to Public international Law 2, London.

Hague Convention for the Pacific Settlement of International Disputes. (1899). Available at: <https://www.loc.gov/law/help/us-treaties/bevans/m-ust000001-0230.pdf> [accessed: 8th November 2023]

Hague Convention for the Pacific Settlement of International Disputes. (1907). Available at: <https://cil.nus.edu.sg/rp/il/pdf/1907%20The%20Hague%20Convention%20for%20the%20Pacific%20Settlement%20of%20International%20Disputes-pdf.pdf> [accessed: 8th December 2023]

Kohen, Marcelo.(2013). *Interaction between diplomatic and judicial means at the initiation of proceedings*. In: De Chazournes, Laurence Boisson, Kohen, Marcelo and

Vinuales, Jorge E. (eds.). Diplomatic and judicial means of dispute settlement. MartinusNijhoff, Leiden, Boston.

Lapidoth, Ruth. Some reflections on peaceful means for the settlement of inter-state disputes. Georgetown University Law Center. Available at: <http://ciwr.ucanr.edu/files/186748.pdf> [accessed: 7th November 2023]

Merrills, J.G. (2011). International dispute settlement. 5th ed. Cambridge University Press.

Murithi, Tim. (2015). The failure of the UN Security Council in creating the framework conditions for mediation. Paper presented at the International Mediation Conference, 2-4 June 2015, University of Pretoria, South Africa, Centre for Mediation, Department for Political Sciences.

Murphy, Sean D. (2002). United States practice in International Law. Volume 1: 1999-2001. Cambridge University Press.

Muhammad Fahmy (nd) international conflict and its repercussions on regional conflicts, an analytical study of the struggle between the two poles of power and their role in third world conflicts, a model for the study of the Iraqi-Iranian war.

Peck, Connie. (1996). The United Nations as a dispute settlement system: improving mechanisms for the prevention and resolution of conflict. Kluwer Law International, The Hague.

Petersman, Ernst-Ulrich. (2004). Justice as Conflict resolution: proliferation, fragmentation and decentralization of dispute settlement in international trade. *EUI Working Paper LAW No.2004/10*. European University Institute, Florence, Department of Law.

Palmer, Geoffrey. (2012). Perspectives on international dispute settlement from a participant, *VUWLR*, Vol.43.

Peters, Anne. (2003). International dispute settlement: a network of cooperational duties. *EJIL*, Vol.14, No.1: 1-34.

Rosenne, Shabtai. (2006). The law and practice of the International Court of Justice 1920-2005. 4th ed. MartinusNijhoff, Leiden.

Rousseau Charles. (1982). Public International Law, translated into Arabic by Shukrullah Khalifa, Al-Ahlia Publishing House, Beirut.

Sander, Frank E.A. (2014). *Alternative dispute resolution in the United States: An overview*. In: Betancourt, Julio Cesar, and Crook, Jason A. (eds.) ADR, Arbitration, and Mediation: A collection of essays. CIARB Chartered Institute of Arbitrators. Author House UK.

Simmonds, Kenneth R. (1987). Public International Arbitration – Roundtable, 22 Texas International Law Journal.

Strutt, Keith. (2014). Mediation vs. negotiation. The Driver Trett Digest. Driver Group, London. Available at: <https://www.driver-group.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/BYTE-9-MEDIATION-VS-NEGOTIATION.pdf> [accessed: 6th November 2023]

Suhail Hussein A (1985). International disputes: A study of the rules of settling international disputes by peaceful means, Publishing House, Dar Al-Qadisiyah Press. Baghdad.

United Kingdom vs. Russia. 1905. *Incident in the North Sea*. 1 Hague Court Report 403

Ury, William, Brett, Jeanne M., Goldberg, Stephen B. (1988). Getting disputes resolved: designing systems to cut the costs of conflict. Jossey-Bass. University of Michigan.

Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1155 UNTS 331. 8ILM 679. (1969). Available at: <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/Volume%201155/volume-1155-I-18232-English.pdf> [accessed: 10th December 2023]

Vienna Convention on Succession of States in Respect of Treaties 1946 UNTS 3. (1978). Available at: http://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/conventions/3_2_1978.pdf [accessed: 9th November 2023]